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Impact of Administrative Tenacity on Nigeria Paramilitary Agencies: A Case Study of Nigeria Security & Civil Defense Corps

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ABSTRACT: The central focus of this research is to examine the major roles of civil defense corps in security administration in Nigeria and the challenges facing the social order, peace and stability of the people as we are in the threshold of the millennium in the 21st century. The entire security architecture of Nigeria is face with myriads of challenges due to the tidal waves of criminal activities and general insecurity that pose serious threats to the corporate existence of the country. These challenges and the incapacitation of the extant security outfits necessitated the conception and delivery of the child of necessity named Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps in 2003 under President Olusegun Obasanjo supplement the efforts of other security outfits. This study found that the Corps was inhibited by factors like dearth of manpower, under utilization of intellectuals among others based on the foregoing the Corps lacks the necessary weapons and gadgets to check the rising wave of crime in the society especially the with the emergence of Boko Haram in Northern Nigeria and militants in the Niger Delta.

Keywords: Traditional Rulers, Challenges, Security, Impacts, Administration, Northern Nigeria

I. INTRODUCTION

The relevance of security in relation to human survival, national stability and sustainable development cannot be over emphasised. In modern times, placing premium on the safety of citizens has become the hallmark of any leader or society that wishes to be perceived as democratic, civilized and advanced in the progressive sense. Furthermore, ensuring the protection of the lives, property and resources of citizens from the encumbrances of threat and danger has become the major pre-occupation of governments that wish to be adjudged or evaluated as successful (Omah, 2013, p. 5). In recent years, Nigeria has been experiencing serious incidents of security threats. In the same vein, Nigeria has continued to be affected directly or indirectly by the dynamics of the global environment with attendant national security concerns that border on virtually all aspects of our national life. These concerns often translate to matters that require the employment of security agencies (especially the armed forces and the police). While some of these threats may be considered minor, others may pose serious danger to the unity and stability of the nation. The internal security threats to Nigeria include terrorism, kidnapping, indigene-settler conflict, ethno-religious conflict, pipeline vandalism and armed robbery.

Others are corruption, transnational crimes, political thuggery and assassination, cross-border

banditry, sea robbery, cattle rustling, herdsman and farmers' clashes and proliferation of small arms. These internal security challenges necessitated the Nigerian government to deploy the military in managing them. However, the military cannot do it alone. Hence, the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC) have been mandated to assist the military in managing threats to internal security in the country.

The entire security architecture of Nigeria is face with myriads of challenges due to the tidal waves of criminal activities and general insecurity that pose serious threats to the corporate existence of the country. These challenges and the incapacitation of the extant security outfits necessitated the conception and delivery of the child of necessity named Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps in 2003 under President Olusegun Obasanjo supplement the efforts of other security outfits.

What is security? Security maintenance is broadly classified into two major management aspects such as direct and indirect matters. They are safety and protection of lives and property and dispute resolution mechanism. The issue of security is the principal purview of state as enshrined in the 1999 constitution (as amended) to include the roles of government in the provision of security and protection to the lives and properties of its citizens. These cardinal objectives are responded to at various levels by its agencies at (national, state and local government levels). Each of these tiers of government has specific agents and institutions in charge of control and administration of security for the citizens. For instance, the army and its units are meant for the protection of the country from external attacks, the police provide internal security and the maintenance of the law and order for the good of the populace.

There are other para-military agencies like the Department of Security Service (DSS), the National Intelligence Agency (N.I.A), the Defence Intelligence Agency (DIA) the Customs, the Immigration, the Federal Road Safety Commission, the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps, the border patrol commission, and at the international community we have the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), the African Union (A.U), The United Nation Organization (U.N.O) provide peace and the enforcement, peace resolution and ceasefire management or agreement. The Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corp is one of such agencies invested by the government to provide security and defence for people survival, the concern about this research is on the role and the responsibilities of the civil defence in securing Nigeria. Specifically, the research aims at x-raying the challenges faced by the organization in the millennium for the 21st century emerging crimes and operations of the militants and insurgents.

Background of the Study

Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps is a para-military agency of the Government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria that is commissioned to provide measures against threat and any form of attack or disaster against the nation and its citizenry. The corps is statutorily empowered by lay Act No. 2 of 2003 and amended by Act 6 of 4th June 2007. They are charged with the following roles and responsibilities of securing the state and the people for peace, justice, freedom, fair play and orderliness: The principal focus of the corps is in the area of broad based information networking monitoring of movement of persons; vandalism of all types; execution of all assignments as may be directed by the parent ministry in the interest of government such as monitoring and supervision of private guard companies.

Again, the Corps are charged with the responsibility to focus on complete rescue operations, crisis managements and complimentary security roles with security outfits such as the SSS, NIA, NPF, the Army, Immigrations, prisons service, as indicated in the gazette or as assigned by government from time to time. A hierarchical structure of command and control was designed with the Commandant-General as the Head.

Nigeria in recent times has witnessed an unprecedented level of insecurity and this has made national security threat to be a major issue for the government and has prompted huge allocation of the national budget to security (Achumba, Ighomereho and Akpor-Robaro, 2013). Successive Governments

had set up security mechanism to tackle security challenges facing the citizens as well as social infrastructure put in place by the government (Adishi and Hunga, 2017). As a matter of fact, insecurity to a large extent is one of the factors affecting the country's developments. To this end, Godly and Wilfred (2012) observed that, in Nigeria of today new forms of violent crimes have become common: These includes kidnapping (usually adult or privileged people's napping) for ransom, Boko Haram bombings, rape, political violence, arson, burglary and pipeline vandalism.

Oil pipeline vandalism has become a common phenomenon and has been reported in several countries of the world, this includes countries such as Indonesia, US, UK, Canada, Iran and Iraq (Davies et al., 2009; Hosmer, Stanton, & Beane, 1997; Parfomak 2004); Russia and Former Soviet Union (FSU) (ESMAP 2003); Columbia, Saudi Arabia and Nigeria (Lia & Kajok, 2004). Hosmer et al. (1997) argued that some attacks may result in substantial oil spills in sensitive locations hard to reach for facility operators to repair. Also, response efforts may be prevented by communities or vandals. Oil pipeline vandalism is particularly widespread in Nigeria (Adebayo & Dada, 2008, Jasper 2009). Obgeni (2012) opined that a total of 16,083 pipeline breaks were recorded within the last 10 years adding that while 398 pipeline breaks representing 2.4 percent were due to ruptures, the activities of vandals accounted for 15,685 breaks which translated to about 97.5 percent of the total number of cases. The statistics above is corroborated by the 2013 annual report of the Nigerian Extractive Industry Transparency Initiative (NEITI), that Nigeria lost a total of 10.9 billion US Dollars to oil theft between 2009 and 2011 (NEITI, 2013; Onoja, 2013).

The security of these oil facilities is imperative as the perpetrators of oil pipeline vandalism are mostly the criminal syndicates who are motivated by the desire to loot oil products for material gain. Hence, the responsibility to ensure the security of these pipelines is part of the duties of the various security agencies such as the police, armed forces and Nigerian Security and Civil Defense Corps (Adishi and Hunga, 2017). The Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps is a Para-military agency of the government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Part of its obligations is to protect and prevent vandalism of major government infrastructure including the oil pipelines (Adishi and Hunga, 2017). As an internal paramilitary agency, the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC) established by Act of 2003, NSCDC had also been assigned to play crucial roles in grassroots security system and nation building (Uthman, 2016). It has power to arrest with warrant or without warrant, detain, investigate and institute legal proceedings against any person who is reasonably suspected to have committed an offence, investigate and take necessary step to forestall any planned act of terrorism and report same to appropriate federal security agency among others (Abolurin 2010:3).

Uthman (2016) noted that since the formation of the corps, it has performed tremendously in the area of crime prevention. Chidozie (2009) observes that Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps have recorded a significant achievement and commitment in discharging their duties without arms. According to him, Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps has done satisfactory work in the areas like escort/public security of well-meaning Nigerians and foreigners, carrying out anti-vandalisation, arresting and prosecuting of vandals, restoration of riot and conflict areas among others. It is also noted however that, the outfit (NSCDC) has paraded several suspected illegal bunkerers and operators of illegal refineries in several parts of the country especially in the Niger Delta region leading to the destruction or recovery of several barges, canoes, speed and large wooden boats (Ogodo, 2012). Despite the contributions of NSCDC in combating oil pipeline vandalism, many factors have been identified by

scholars to be responsible for the ineffectiveness on the part of NSCDC in the discharge of their duties in the protection of oil facilities across the country. The organization is observed by Godly and Wilfred (2012) to lack adequate manpower, modern technological equipment, adequate training and fund.

The erstwhile Commandant General of NSCDC Gana M (2016) “Your welfare is paramount to me”. The incumbent Commandant General Ahmed Audi, PhD, had taking care of 7yrs and more overdue of promotion within 100days in office, these feet could not be achieved by the previous two heads of the agency in the last 6 years, not because the welfare of personnel was not important to them, but because the Administrative tenacity was missing. Having a terrific administrative team to work with will make Audi second to none and possibly beat the Abolurin record. Intake year/set just has Audi has started on Name tags will be helpful if all this sets are sent to the existing colleges for retraining and orientation even if it's a week. Powerfully structured database at zero cost is possible which will eliminate continuous call for collation of data on a weekly or monthly basis and save the organization from errors and deliberate attempt to play smart for promotions; with training for Administrative staff all the way from top. Persons with strong intellectuals should be utilized in Colleges to drive home Audi's dream. Colleges can metamorphose to Paramilitary Colleges with relevant approval from Ministry of education and Nigeria University Commission.

Agency will now have a functional college possibly in line with the dream of Jomo one of the funding father's in the then Lagos Civil Defence. First school Leaving Certificate, Senior School Certificate and Bachelor's Degree. All can be products of the existing colleges. Possibility to expand into other states cannot be ruled out. This will become source of revenue. NCE holders in the service will be judiciously utilized.

Thus this study investigates the role and challenges of Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Corps (NSCDC) in combating boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria. Various studies have been carried out in Sub-Saharan Africa and Nigeria on the dimensions of pipeline sabotage, actors, health and economic implications of pipeline vandalism but there appears to be a dearth of research on the impact and challenges of NSCDC in combating boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria.

The main objective of the study is to investigate the impact of administrative tenacity on Nigeria paramilitary agencies using Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Corps (NSCDC) as a case study in combating the emergence of Boko Haram in Northern Nigeria, Fulani Herdsmen in Southwest and militants in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. However, in attempt to achieve this, the research specific objectives are to: examines the role of NSCDC in internal security management, identify the role-played by the Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Corps in combating Fulani-herdsmen and kidnapping in Nigeria, examine the challenges militating against optimum performance of NSCDC in combating banditry and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria and highlight the implications of Boko Haram in the Nigerian society.

The research is divided into five sections. The first is the introductory part, background of the study, statement of the problem, followed by an overview of internal security challenges in Nigeria, the historical background of NSCDC and the constitutional role of NSCDC, historical background and constitutional role of NSCDC. The third section examines the NSCDC and internal security management, challenges of NSCDC in internal security management, methodology and theoretical framework. The fourth section examines data analysis and interpretation and discussion of findings. The final section is the conclusion and recommendations.

Statement of the Problem

Boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism are problem of urgent attention by all and sundry in Nigeria. These can cause issues like under-development, malnutrition, oil spillage, and scarcity of fuel for transportation as well as high cost of purchase of the products among others (Umar and Uthman, 2017). Countries today cannot survive without natural resources especially crude oil products. The issue of insecurity accruing from Boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism has affected the revenue the Nigerian government generates from various firms especially oil industries in Nigeria. Nigeria lost a total of 10.9 billion US Dollars to oil theft between 2009 and 2011 (NEITI, 2013; Onoja, 2013). This loss indicates the significance of vandalism other related insecurities as a veritable problem in Nigeria. The implications of oil pipeline vandalism vis-a-vis Nigeria's security has been vividly demonstrated by its nexus with economic, environmental, and humanitarian losses and consequences (Onuoha, 2009). Between 2010 and 2012, total of 2,787 lines breaks were reported on pipelines belonging to the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), resulting in a loss of 157.81mt of petroleum products worth about ₦12.53billion. Scholars have agreed that oil production is very essential for the development of a country. Oil pipeline vandalism has also led to high incidence of oil spillage in Nigeria over the years.

It is no longer news that the activities of the Boko Haram and other similar political and or religious sects have often led to the loss of properties, lives, and even the breakdown of laws and order, peace and security in the Nigerian society at large. It has been observed that a lot of attacks have been made onto many states, which include even the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. What puzzles most observers is the fact that most of these attacks are not carried out by suicide bombers yet the culprits often get away unharmed. This leaves a big question mark in our security agencies as regards to their duty in the protection of lives and properties, and the procurement of weapons of mass destruction to combat this menace which is eating deep into the Nigerian society today.

Without being said, Boko Haram crisis does not have any advantage instead it is a vicious and nefarious activities carried out by individuals for their selfish desires, the motivating factor being to control the religious and political power. This incidence of pipeline vandalism has also resulted in environmental degradation which jeopardizes the land, vegetation and habitation of the affected area. This has been exemplified in desolation of farmlands, loss of aquatic and wild lives, as well as water and air pollution. These conditions have implications for public health and safety of the people. It is the hope of this study that the problem of Boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in the country can be resolved having study the roles of the NSCDC in combating this menace with attention of the challenges and what can be done to improve and have a total defeat in the war against insecurities so that the economic and social development expected from the oil sector can be achieved in Nigeria.

II. OVERVIEW OF INTERNAL SECURITY CHALLENGES IN NIGERIA

Nigeria is currently experiencing some form of insecurity which threatens the country's democracy, with great potential of impacting its national development negatively. The spate of insecurity and threats to lives and properties in Nigeria has reached alarming proportions despite the increasing viability of the Nigerian Police and the military in the management of internal conflicts (The US Department of State 2008; Omede2011; Minimah2015; Johnson 2016). The following are some of the internal security challenges confronting Nigeria today.

Ethno-religious Conflict

The manifestations of upsurge in ethno-religious conflicts in Nigeria could be captured in the various violent conflicts that erupted in different parts of the country immediately after the inauguration of a new democratic government in May 1999. Cases of violent religious crisis were recorded in some parts of the country with ethnic dimensions. These crises which were mostly recorded in northern Nigeria have been between Christians and Muslims, thus making that part of the country notorious for ethno-religious crises (Odoma2014). For instance, the February 21, 2009, ethno-religious conflict at Makama New Extension in Bauchi State claimed over ten lives, more than 400 houses burnt and several properties destroyed (Ugwueze, 2016).

Terrorism/Religious Fundamentalism

Since the end of the Civil War in 1970, no other internal security threat has dominated national discourse like the current Boko Haram terrorism. The activities of this sect and others with similar extremist ideologies/narratives have been a great concern to the government and ordinary Nigerians. The sect seeks to impose what it terms as an absolute Islamic ideology on the country, starting with Borno State. Their methods have mimicked those of other extremist groups across the globe and involved the sophisticated use of improvised explosive devices (IEDs), suicide bombings, beheadings, mass abductions and the sensational use of the media (Minimah, 2015).

Indigene-Settler Conflict

The indigene-settler dichotomy is one problem that has made many Nigerians ask whether or not their citizenship is anything they can be proud of (Odoma, 2014). Although crises relating to indigene-settler questions have reared their ugly head in many parts of Nigeria over the years, the worst cases were recorded in Plateau State in recent years. The Hausa-Fulani, who have lived for years in Jos, see reason to lay claim to Jos North Local Government, while three other tribes Anaguta, Berom and Afizere also lay claim to the same on the condition that the Hausa-Fulani met them there as indigenes (Odoma, 2014). This indigene-settler conflict has claimed hundreds of lives and unquantifiable resources in the series of violent clashes and reprisal attacks.

Kidnapping/Hostage-Taking

Kidnapping and hostage-taking is still prevalent, especially in the South-East and South-South Zones. These started as political actions in the South-South meant to attract external and governmental attention to the plight of the long neglected region, but it has ended up as commercial actions in the South-East for criminal enrichment of the self (Nwolise, 2014). These nefarious activities, no doubt, have a negative impact on the level of socio-economic development in the affected areas.

Illegal Arms Proliferation

The alarming rate of small arms trafficking and proliferation nationwide has contributed to changing the face of conflicts in Nigeria. Thus, the internal proliferation of arms has threatened Nigeria's security. Security reports on various conflicts have implicated both Nigerians and foreign mercenaries from across the borders in the trade in arms and use of the same. In the same vein, the capacity of local arms manufacturers and dealers to produce and sell arms within Nigeria is increasing by the day. These arms are mostly used to perpetrate political violence, kidnapping, armed robbery and other criminal acts within the country.

The Niger Delta Crisis

The security challenge posed by the emergence of Niger Delta militants is enormous. The militant groups include Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), Niger Delta People's Volunteer Force (NDPVF) and Niger Delta Vigilante (NDV). Their modus operandi has defied national security mechanisms, and the strategic dexterity with which they operate, coupled with the sophisticated nature of their weapons, has raised such questions as to the source of their military training and experience. As a result of the conflict in the region, lives and resources have been wasted; hostage-taking, shoot-outs between soldiers and armed militant groups, petroleum pipeline sabotage and so on have led to production shut-in and deferment (Omeje, 2006; Johnson, 2016). Other manifestations of insecurity in contemporary Nigeria include armed robbery, political thuggery and assassinations, cult clashes, urban crimes, vandalisation of electricity equipment, cross-border banditry, oil theft and pipeline vandalisation, herdsman and farmer's clashes and transnational crimes.

Historical Background and Constitutional Role of NSCDC

The NSCDC was established on May 23, 1967, during the Nigerian Civil War. Then, it was initially referred to as the Lagos Civil Defence Committee charged with the fundamental responsibility of precaution during the Civil War. However, the Charter of April 6, 1968, made it possible for states that wished to establish the Corps within their jurisdiction to do so (Abolurin, 2010, p. 132). However, the promulgation of the Act known as NSCDC Act No. 2 of 2003 and amended by Act 6 of June 4, 2007, makes the Corps a full-fledged paramilitary outfit of the government under the then Federal Ministry of Internal Affairs, now Ministry of Interior, and by this enactment the Corps now has some statutory responsibilities to perform.

Some of the constitutional roles of NSCDC as contained in the establishing Act (as amended) are to:

1. Assist in the maintenance of peace and order and in the protection and rescuing of the civil population during periods of emergency.
2. Recommend to the minister the registration of private guard companies.
3. From time to time, inspect the premises of private guard companies, their training facilities and approve the same if it is up to standard.
4. Supervise and monitor the activities of all private guard companies and keep a register for that purpose:
 - a. Periodically, organize workshops and training courses for private guard companies.
 - b. Seal up any private guard company which operates without a valid licence.
5. Maintain 24-hour surveillance over infrastructures, site and projects for the federal, state and local governments:
 - a. Enter and search any premises and seize any material suspected to have been used in vandalisation or the suspected process of vandalisation.
 - b. Enter and search premises of any suspected illegal dealer in petroleum products or material used by the Power Holding Company of Nigeria, postal services, Nigeria telecommunications or for any other public utility or infrastructure.

6. Have power to arrest with or without a warrant, detain, investigate and institute legal proceedings by or in the name of the attorney general of the Federal Republic of Nigeria against any person who is reasonably suspected to have committed an offence under the Act or is involved in any:
 - a. Criminal activity.
 - b. Chemical poison or oil spillage, nuclear waste and poisoning.
 - c. Industry espionage or fraud
 - d. Activity aimed at frustrating any government programme or policy.
 - e. Riot, civil disorder, revolt, strike or religious unrest.
 - f. Power transmission line, or oil pipelines, Nigerian Postal Service (NIPOST) cables, equipment, water board pipes or equipment vandalism.
7. Monitor the activities of religious bodies and trade associations.
8. Monitor, investigate and take every necessary step to forestall any planned act of terrorism, particularly:
 - a. Cult and ethnic militia activities.
 - b. Criminal activities aimed at depriving citizens of their properties or lives.
 - c. Syndicate activity aimed at defrauding the federal state or local governments.
9. Monitor, investigate and take every necessary step to forestall any act of terrorism and report the same to the appropriate federal security agency.
10. Provide necessary warning for the civilian population in times of danger.
11. Evacuate the civilian population from danger areas.
12. Provide and manage shelters for civilians during period of emergency.
13. Assist in the decontamination and in the taking of precautionary measures during any period of emergency.
14. Carry out rescue operations and control volatile situations.
15. Assist in the provision of emergency medical services, including first aid, during any period of emergency.
16. Detect and demarcate any danger area.
17. Assist the federal and state fire services in fire-fighting operations.
18. Assist in the distribution of emergency supplies.
19. Provide assistance to restore and maintain order in distressed areas in any period of emergency.
20. Assist in repairing indispensable public utilities during any period of emergency.
21. Provide intelligence information to the military on any matter relating to:
 - a. Crime control generally.
 - b. Riot, disorder, revolt, strike or religious unrest.
 - c. Subversive activity by members of the public aimed at frustrating any government programme or policy.

- d. Industrial action and strike aimed at paralysing government activities.
- e. Any other matter as may be directed by the minister.
- f. Have power to arrange and mediate in the settlement of disputes among willing members of the public (Abolurin, 2010).

III. NSCDC AND INTERNAL SECURITY MANAGEMENT

The Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC) since its inception has evolved from an insignificant status to an enviable height and has become an organization to be reckoned with in the area of internal security management. The worsening security situation in the country where acts like vandalisation, oil bunkering, kidnapping, cult clashes, violence and bombing are now the order of the day posits that Nigeria's internal security is being threatened by organized criminals who have devised modern techniques of carrying out their nefarious acts and by other cases of insecurity that are being perpetrated by ordinary citizens. Thus, the task of securing the nation cannot be left only to the Armed Forces and the Nigeria Police.

The Corps on many occasions has performed creditably well to actualize the mandate given to it in the area of checking of vandalism, in maintaining peace and conflict resolutions, in resource management and in being proactive in countering terrorism. The Corps has worked assiduously to reduce to the minimum acts of vandalism in the oil industry as the former Commandant-General, Dr. Abolurin, in his interview with Leadership News, confirmed the prosecution of not less than 30 culprits in the first two months of 2012, which has proven that the Corps is not leaving any stone unturned in that direction (Leadership News, 2012). Also worthy of commendation in this regard is the contribution of NSCDC in the containment of riots and protests that greeted the 2012 oil subsidy removal in Nigeria. Crime has been identified as a social problem and constitutes a threat to Nigeria's national security (Aderinto, 2002). The responsibility of prosecuting criminal offenders was solely that of the Nigeria Police Force. Prior to the constitutional approval of the NSCDC as an agency with legal rights to prosecute criminal offenders, offenders were arrested, investigated and handed over to the police for prosecution. Pursuant to the promulgation of the NSCDC Act of 2007, the agency is empowered to prosecute criminal offenders at the constitutional law courts. To be sure, the NSCDC has always been co-opted into a different Joint Task Force in preventing criminal activities.

More importantly, criminals do not live in isolation; they live among other citizens within the same community. For security agencies to be effective in crime control, they need information, and this information may not come voluntarily. In view of this, there is the need to interact with the public to extract information from them. The NSCDC in this regard did this within the context of grass-roots intelligence information gathering. In the same vein, one of the methods of NSCDC in crime control during conflicts or violence is education. The civil populace is often given orientation on what should be their reactions or responses to various developments that may occur during conflict in order to accelerate the peace process and resettlement of affected people. In the area of humanitarian assistance and managing of relief materials, the NSCDC has been very active. In cases where humanitarian relief materials are allocated to people who suffer losses during conflicts, the NSCDC is one of the prominent government agencies usually directed to protect and oversee the judicious distribution of these materials.

For example, the Corps has assisted in providing humanitarian services in the following cases:

1. Bellview air crash at Lisa Village in Ogun State in 2005.
2. ADC air crash in Abuja Airport in 2006.
3. Dutse River flooding in Jalingo, Taraba State.

4. Prophet Muhammed cartoon riots in Maiduguri, Borno State, and its fallouts in Onitsha, Anambra State, Enugu State and in Aba, Abia State.
5. Pipeline explosion in AbuleEgba in Lagos, December 2006.
6. Bomb blast at the Army Cantonment, Ikeja, Lagos.
7. The Sosoliso air crash in Port-Harcourt.
8. Train derailment and petroleum spillage rescue operation at Apetein Ibadan 2005 (Abolurin, 2007, p. 13).
9. Rescue operation of a nine-year-old boy chained in a church for stealing soup in Ota, Ogun State, July 2016.
10. Collaborated with other security agencies for the rehabilitation of internally displaced persons (IDPs) in the North-East, 2016.
11. The Borno command deployed about 600 Corps to various worship centres in Maiduguri to assure worshippers of their safety during the month of Ramadan, June 2017 (Daily Post.ng).

In addition, the NSCDC has contributed immensely in preventing and mitigating disaster and emergency throughout the country. It has established a Disaster Management Department whose sole responsibility is to raise alarm on disaster and emergency areas. NSCDC has been very active in medical relief, rehabilitation and reconstruction, as well as health care of the people during national functions like sports fiestas, religious crusades and events organised by the government and NGOs. The Corps has defined four areas/issues in disaster management, namely: prevention, preparedness, response and recovery. Preventive measures are undertaken through early warning conducted through aggressive and massive public enlightenment and education in disaster-prone areas. Preparedness is about the machinery put by the Corps to counter the occurrence or mitigate the impact of disaster, whereas response takes the form of search and rescue operations designed to salvage lives, properties and environment.

Recovery entails reliefs, rehabilitation and reconstruction aimed at restoring normalcy (Alao, 2017). For instance, the Corps participated in the management of internally displaced persons (IDPs) from the Boko Haram terrorist attacks. The Corps not only safeguards their lives and properties from looting but also guards against further attacks. Terrorism and violence are the major security threats to Nigeria's internal security. These include violent riots, kidnapping, explosive bombing, assassination, incendiary attacks, herdsman-farmers' clashes and cultism. There is an upsurge of terrorism occasioned by the Boko Haram insurgency which has led to loss of lives and property. The NSCDC has discharged its mandate on terrorism through public enlightenment, education and intelligence gathering. The Corps has collected intelligence on the activities of different terrorist groups and passed the same to the appropriate authorities such as the Army, Navy, Police and the Air Force. Also relevant to this discussion is the training of the Anti-Bomb and Counter-Terrorism units.

The Corps, in line with its mandate, has sent its officers on counter-insurgency training overseas and in order to competently forestall all subversive activities, the agency has set up a unit to coordinate all its anti-terrorism and counter-insurgency operations. Since the return of the Corps personnel from overseas training, they have assisted in reducing kidnapping, cultism and, to some extent, foiled several terrorist attacks and helped in assisting victims of bomb blasts. The Corps cooperated with other security agencies to free a Lagos Monarch Oniba of Iba Land, Oba YushauOseni, from abductors in 2016. In the same vein, the Corps, in collaboration with the Kwara State Police Command, arrested about 40 suspects

in connection with a clash among the Aiye and Eiye cult groups at the Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin, in 2015 (Daily Trust 2015). Of late, the Borno Command of the NSCDC said it has discovered “Count Down Timers” used by Boko Haram terrorists to detonate explosives. The Commandant of the Corps, Mr Ibrahim Abdullahi, said that the instruments were discovered by men of the Disaster Management Unit of the Command at the scene of bomb blasts in Kalari area of the state capital (www.garanews.com/2017).

The protection of vital key infrastructures is one of the constitutional responsibilities of the NSCDC. It is imperative to note that the security and safety of Nigerians have been undermined by the activities of vandals motivated by a variety of reasons, namely: political, economic, vengeance, sabotage, conspiracy and the rest. Vandals have destroyed petroleum pipelines, Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) high-tension cables, rail lines and railings on bridges, public vehicles, properties and utilities, among others. For instance, the Corps revealed plans by some persons to attack investments of Mobile Telecommunication Network (MTN) in Bayelsa State as a reprisal following the xenophobia attack on Nigerians in South Africa. The anti-vandalism role of the NSCDC is a key mandate which the Corps has carried out with competence and result. The Corps has carried out their role through media campaigns, public enlightenment and orientation, rating vandals’ activities, vulnerability analysis, threat analysis, planning and preparedness (Alao, 2017). The success recorded by 2008, reported that the Corps arrested over 300 pipelines’ vandals in riverine areas like Ebonyi, Abia, Warri, Ondo and other axes. The paper also reported that in Abia State, over 200 arrests were made and 53 cases are in the law court (National Mirror, 2008, p. 24). Also, the Corps resorts to the use of force where clear evidence of pipeline vandalisation is detected and the culprits can be identified. In this regard, arrests are made and the vandals are taken to court for prosecution.

In the area of private guard companies, the NSCDC has contributed to safety and security through the registration, monitoring and supervision of these companies. It is a known fact that state security agencies cannot cope with the volume, nature and dynamics of common crimes, hence the emergence of private guards to provide security to clients for a fee. The private guard companies have been established in every part of the country providing services for clients. However, the issue of private guard companies fizzling out or being unable to arrest culprits when crimes are traced to their doorsteps has become a thing of the past. This is because the NSCDC makes sure that no private guard company is floated without prior registration, training, inspections and renewal of registration licence. Thus, the NSCDC in this area has enhanced the security service delivery of these companies, enthroned professionalism and created a congenial environment for private guard companies and their clients.

The Corps has also sensitized the private guard companies to make meaningful contribution to Nigeria’s national security. The Corps within a year licensed 285 private guards companies, sealed 96 and renewed 600, while 210 are still waiting to be licensed (aljahirahnews.com/appraising-giant-stride). It has also reduced to a minimal level crimes and other social vices in Nigerian urban and rural settings. For instance, the Corps arrested a tanker load of suspected adulterated fuel in the Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State in May 2017. The Corps in collaboration with the Police, Army and Air Force recovered over 200 cows and sheep from suspected rustlers in the Birnin Gwari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The animals were recovered during a raid at a forest in Buruku village, following intelligence reports from patriotic residents concerning the activities of suspected rustlers in the area in May 2017 (www.channelstv.com).

Finally, the NSCDC has participated immensely in elections for the purpose of enhancing its smooth conduct. The Corps encourages voters and politicians to conform to the rules and norms of Independent National Electoral Commission’s guidelines. This is aimed at ensuring a peaceful polity even after the conduct of elections. It should be noted that the role of NSCDC is not only during elections but also before and after elections. In the 2011 general elections, a sizeable number of NSCDC personnel were noticed in all the 36 states of the federation and the federal capital territory (Abuja), making sure

peace and tranquility existed among spectators and actors. The Corps helped in the transfer of equipment and materials (sensitive and non-sensitive) needed for the purpose of the elections. In addition, the Corps recorded a significant achievement during the 2015 general elections. The NSCDC deployed its officers for effective monitoring before, during and after the elections. The deployment of Corps personnel was to identify black spots with the collaborative efforts of all security apparatuses in order to ensure hitch-free polls. In short, the deployment of the Corps personnel was to ensure effective protection of residents and government installations against attack during the polls. About 60,000 of the Corps personnel were deployed for this task. In the same vein, the Corps deployed dogs which were used to detect improvised explosive devices (IEDs). The agency also put in place the use of forensic psychologists and the deployment of modern surveillance vehicles to ensure a peaceful atmosphere for the conduct of the 2015 general elections (<http://www.airmaxfreedom.com/nikeairmaxgriffey>).

Challenges of NSCDC in Internal Security Management

The challenges confronting the NSCDC within the context of internal security management are enormous. These challenges must be seen as problems that must be attended to urgently in order to restore the reputation of the country that has been dragged in the mud before the comity of nations owing to the present internal security predicament in Nigeria.

First, the NSCDC is ill equipped to meet the present internal security challenges in the country. The most common weapons available to the agency according to a personal interview with an officer of NSCDC are G3 and AK 47. It was observed that the Nigerian Army trained the NSCDC personnel on the stripping and assembling of G3 and AK 47 rifles, description of the G3 rifle, arms maintenance and shooting positions. However, the criminals that the Corps daily confront come up with more sophisticated weapons, making it difficult for the Corps to overcome them in some cases.

Second, the Corps has serious challenges in the area of logistics. Not only those vehicles are in short supply, the ones that are available cannot match the terrain on which they operate mostly. The vehicles are either old or by design not good for paramilitary operations. For instance, the oil pipeline vandals operate inside the bush, sometimes mostly rough terrain that only vehicles with high-ground clearance and four-wheel drive could effectively be used for operations. In view of this situation, the Corps should be equipped with enough vehicles of paramilitary design.

Third, the state governments have not been fully supporting the NSCDC as a law-enforcement agency. The federal government cannot do it alone. This is why the state governments have been assisting the Nigeria Police Force with patrol vehicles, armoured personnel carrier, bullet-proof vests and helicopters. Thus, for effective performance, state governments should extend the same to the NSCDC.

Fourth, some law-enforcement agencies which have been regularized before NSCDC do act as if they are superior to the NSCDC. The NSCDC is now in rivalry with the police. The police authorities have been protesting the establishment of the NSCDC, stressing that the Corps is performing their duties. While the police have had more clashes with the Army, Navy and the Air Force, they also engage in a serious superiority contest with the NSCDC (Abolurin, 2010: 334).

Other areas calling for urgent attention are:

- The need for the NSCDC to focus on long-term strategy on grass-roots intelligence security and civil defence operations.
- The need to diligently assess new and emerging threats to national security

- The need to develop the ability to initiate measures in terms of intelligence networking and information gathering both as short- and long-term projections.
- The need to monitor and upgrade existing security mechanisms to commensurate with the level of identified threat, especially in this state of heightened insecurity in Nigeria (<http://www.nscdc.gov.ng>).

Methodology

The study utilized the quantitative and qualitative research method to investigate impact on Nigeria paramilitary agencies of NSCDC in combating boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria. It adopted a descriptive survey using structured questionnaire for systematic empirical investigation of the phenomena under study. The population of the study was one hundred respondents comprising members of the agency (NSCDC) and members of the host communities across Nigeria where incidents of boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism were experienced. Thus the purposive sampling technique was used to focus on administering copies of questionnaires to members of the group in charge of the fight against boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria. The participants majorly are the officials of NSCDC deployed to combat boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria.

Data were sourced from both primary and secondary data via relevant books, journals, conference papers, newspaper publications, government documentations and online materials. The secondary data were supplemented with personal interviews of some NSCDC personnel, which served as tangible sources of insight into the role of NSCDC in internal security management.

Theoretical Framework

Strain Theory

The strain theory, propounded by Robert Merton, is used as theoretical framework for this study. The theory was developed by Merton (1957) using Durkheim's concept of anomie. Merton posited that when a legitimate means, for example (job employment) of acquiring a culturally defined goal (money) is limited by the structure of society, the resulting strain may lead to crime. As such, strain theory explains criminality as a result of blocked opportunities or impediments which are put on the way of people consciously or unconsciously by the society or government. This leads to social disorganization, which makes the individual (unemployed youth) to try in achieving the societal goals (employment) through deviant means (criminality). To such individual, any institutionalized means is legitimate as long as the end justifies the means.

In our attempt to situate this study within a specific theoretical framework that will be appropriate in explaining the relationship as regard the topic on the challenges of NSCDC in combating pipeline vandalism; its impact on Nigeria economy; the general strain theory is adopted. Strain theorist believes that most people share similar values and goals. They want to earn money, have a nice home, drive a great car, and wear stylish clothes. They also want to care for their families and educate their children. Unfortunately, the ability to achieve these personal goals are stratified by social economic class, while the affluent may live a big life, the poor are shut out from achieving their goals, because they cannot always get what they want, they begin to feel frustrated and angry towards governmental policies, organization and individual who they feel as the ones that are thwarting their goal directed behavior a condition referred to as strain (Adishi, 2016). Generally, strain is related to criminal motivation of people who feel

economically and socially humiliated, annihilated and may perceived that they have the right to humiliate the aggrieved.

In Nigeria today, after long years of injustices melted on the Vandals and bottled emotion as a result of suppression by the military, the advent of democracy which allow people to express themselves as a result of democratic windows of self-expression and urge for fundamental human rights against the working of the state and security sector generally stressed the working relationship between security sector, government and the citizens, hence high risk factors (strain) and new security challenges. The role of NSCDC is majorly to protect these oil facilities across the country and also to suppress the tendencies of vandals in the society. It has been shown that the officials of NSCDC have not been able to live up to expectation because of some challenges facing them. The theory is relevant to our work which focuses on pipeline vandalism, a crime in the Nigerian society which many would agree today has not just emanated but for reasons of unemployment, poverty, hunger and some other forms of unpleasant welfare. We can therefore argue that the significant of the theory cannot be over emphasizing as it will serve as a framework for the study.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

In this section, the data on the impact on Nigeria paramilitary agencies of Nigeria security and civil defense corps in combating boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria are presented in the tables below.

Results

Table 1: Socio-Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Variables	Frequencies	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	59	59%
Female	41	41%
Total	100	100.0%
Academic Qualification		
School leaving certificate	6	6%
Secondary School Certificate	27	27%
Tertiary Institution	67	67%
Total	100	100.0%

(Source: field survey, 2019)

Table 1 represents socio-demographic characteristics of respondents. Sex distribution of the respondents shows that, 59% are male, while 41% of the respondents are female. This suggests that there were more males in the distribution than females. Furthermore, 40% of the total populations are between the ages of 16 to 25, 22% are between the ages of 26 to 25, 17 % of the respondents are between the ages of 36 to 45 while 21% are 46 years and above.

This shows that the larger parts of the respondents are youth who have better understanding of the issues concerning boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria. Also as observed from the table, the first category of the sampled respondents are just holders of First School Leaving Certificate, they constituted the lowest number in the respondents with just 6 which is 6% of the total respondents. Similarly, another category of respondents are 27 (27%) and these are individuals whose qualifications are Senior Secondary School Certificate. The last set of people constitutes 67 (67%) who are holders of tertiary education certificate. This indicates that most of the respondents are well learned since those with tertiary educational qualification constitutes larger part of the entire population of the study.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents on the role of NSCDC in combating pipeline vandalism in Nigeria

S/N	The role of NSCDC in combating pipeline vandalism in Warri Nigeria.	A (%)	SA (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
1.	NSCDC has been able to restore peace and protect pipelines in Nigeria.	43(43)	57(57)	0	0
2.	The NSCDC have carried out operations on several occasions to combat boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria.	57(57)	40(40)	3(3)	0
3.	The police are very important agency the NSCDC should work with to tackle pipeline vandalism in the country.	43(43)	55(55)	2(2)	0
4.	The NSCDC collaborate with other law enforcement agencies in the country to protect the pipelines in Nigeria.	50(50)	39(39)	9(9)	2(2)
5.	Many people have been caught vandalizing the pipeline on several occasions by the NSCDC.	52(52)	40(40)	6(6)	2(2)

(Source Field Work, 2019)

From the above table, it has shown that the entire respondent (100%) opined that NSCDC have been able to restore peace and protect pipelines in Nigeria as at current situation of the country. It is revealed that 57% and 40% agreed and strongly agreed respectively with the statement that NSCDC have carried out operations on several occasions to combat pipeline vandalism in the country. 98% of the respondents also align with the view that the NSCDC should partner with the police in combating pipeline vandalism in the country. Only 10% of the respondents disagreed that NSCDC collaborate with other security agencies in the country to fight pipeline vandalism, the other 90% support that they collaborate in the fight against pipeline vandalism in the country. The last statement on the questionnaire formulated for research question three is “Many people have been caught vandalizing the pipeline on several occasions by the NSCDC”, according to our analysis, 52% agreed, 40% strongly agreed, 6% disagreed and 2% strongly disagreed. From the above analysis, we can deduce that the role and contribution of NSCDC in the fight against pipeline vandalism cannot be overemphasized. They work hand in hand with other security agencies to ensure that Nigerian Pipelines are safe and the people living around the pipeline area are safe and well secured.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents on the challenges of NSCDC in combating pipeline vandalism in Warri, Nigeria.

S/N	Challenges of NSCDC in combating pipeline vandalism in Nigeria.	A%	SA%	D%	SD%
1.	The location of the pipeline in Warri is strategic and perfect.	45	38	9	8
2.	The problem of pipeline vandalism is very rampant in Warri.	50	20	18	8
3.	Members of the community also contribute to the increase rate of pipeline vandalism by not reporting cases of pipeline vandalism to the appropriate authority.	55	23	17	5
4	The NSCDC is facing problems of lack of trained professional personnel.	48	28	10	14
5.	Some of those who engage in pipeline vandalism are sponsored by some political elites in the community.	51	31	17	1
6.	The NSCDC is facing the problems of inefficient equipment.	18	17	55	10
7.	The NSCDC is facing the problems of corruption.	18	44	28	10
8.	The NSCDC is facing the problems of lack of proper funding in its efforts to combat oil pipeline vandalism in Nigeria.	42	26	20	12
9.	Areas of oil pipelines in the country lacks effective security arrangements.	18	48	28	10

(Source: Field Work, 2019)

In the presentations above, majority of the respondents who are residents of Warri, the study area believed that the location of the pipeline within Warri metropolis is strategic and perfect. In item 1, 70% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed that pipeline vandalism is prevalence in Warri. Also, it is agreed by 55% of the respondents that members of the community also contribute to the increase rate of pipeline vandalism by not reporting cases of pipeline vandalism to the appropriate authority, 23% strongly agreed to this opinion while 17% and 5% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. Item 4 shows that majority of the respondents which total 76% support the assertion that lack of professional personnel is a problem facing NSCDC. 51% and 31% agreed and strongly agreed respectively that most of the pipeline vandals are sponsored by the political elites in the community.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents on the implication of oil pipeline vandalism to Nigeria society

S/N	The implications of pipeline vandalism in the Nigeria society	A%	SA%	D%	SD%
1.	Nigeria had witnessed environmental degradation and loss of economic activities of the communities due to pipeline vandalism.	30	57	8	5
2.	There have been fire disasters and pipeline explosions due to pipeline vandalism in the country.	42	46	4	8
3.	Pipeline vandalism has created the scarcity of oil production in the country.	47	53	0	0
4.	Pipeline vandalism has created environmental pollution to the community.	40	60	0	0
5.	Oil pipeline vandalism has resulted in the wanton killing of government officials and public security agents in Nigeria.	40	45	7	8
6.	Pipeline vandalism constitutes a veritable threat to the Nigeria society as a whole.	39	58	0	3

(Source: Field Work, 2019)

The table above shows that 87% of the total respondents support that Nigeria had witnessed environmental degradation and loss of economic activities of the communities due to pipeline vandalism. In item 2, 42% agreed, 46% strongly agreed, 4% and 8% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that there has been fire disasters and pipeline explosions due to pipeline vandalism in the country. It also revealed that 100% of the respondents support the view that one of the major causes of fuel scarcity in the country is pipeline vandalism. Similarly all the respondents aligned with statement that pipeline vandalism has created environmental pollution to the immediate community. In item 5 where it is stated that Oil pipeline vandalism has resulted in the wanton killing of government officials and public security agents in Nigeria”, 40% of the respondents agreed, 45% strongly agreed, 7% disagreed and 8% strongly disagreed. Lastly, it shows that only 3% of the entire population strongly disagreed that Pipeline vandalism constitutes a veritable threat to the Nigeria society as a whole, the other 97% agreed and strongly agreed with the assertion. The analysis shows large percentage of our correspondents recognized many of the implications pipeline vandalism has caused the country. This is so because in average, 93 out of 100 respondents agreed and strongly agreed with the statements formulated for the purpose of the research questions.

Discussion of Findings

From the analysis so far, it was discovered that NSCDC is a very vital security operative in Nigeria that is mandated with the responsibility of ensuring that the pipelines in the country are safe and members of the immediate community where the pipelines are located across the country should be safe from any harm that could be caused by any form of boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria. It is also evident that the role played by NSCDC are numerous and in line with the submissions of Uthman (2016), Kingdom Sunday Mboho and Tahiri Emmanuel Udousoro (2014) among others research work, our findings show that establishing NSCDC is a welcome development by the government to tackle the menace of boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria. It is also note worthy that this work further agree with the view that Nigerian Security and Civil Defense Corps is saddled with the responsibility of protecting and preventing vandalism of major government infrastructure including the oil pipelines.

This result of the findings also revealed that the view of Chidozie (2009) who observes that NSCDC has been helpful in restoring peace and ensuring safety of the Nigerian Pipeline. It was also discovered from the findings that there have been a collaborative efforts between the NSCDC and other security agencies in tackling oil pipeline vandalism in Nigeria and they have caught several individuals who have vandalize oil pipeline in the country. More revealed in the findings of this work that there are many problems confronting NSCDC in the discharge of their duties and functions in the fight against boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in the country. Having noted that the problem of boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria are rampant in the country and needs urgent attention and corroborating the research work of scholars like Uthman (2016), Kingdom and Tahiri (2014), Chidozie, E. (2009) among others, our work shows that many of the challenges facing NSCDC which need to be tackled are lackadaisical attitude of community members who do not report cases of boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in Nigeria, lack of professionally trained personnel, sponsorship of vandalism by political elites, lack of sufficient and inefficient equipment, high level of corruption in the country and lack of effective security arrangements in the areas where pipelines are situated all over the country.

The findings also revealed that oil pipeline vandalism has had devastating effects on the Nigerian economy. Firstly, its agreed that oil pipeline vandalism have caused issues like environmental degradation, loss of lives and properties, economic disturbances, fire disasters and explosion, fuel scarcity, environmental pollution, killing of government officials and security agencies. In a whole, the vandalism of pipeline is a threat to the Nigerian society as a whole.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, from the findings, and data generated from the respondents, it was observed that the Nigeria security and Civil defense corps perform the following role in Nigeria; to man all the pipelines in the country. They focus on complete rescue operations, crisis management and complimentary security roles and security outfit in the country, they also perform the role of securing the state and the people for peace, justice and orderliness in the country. Also, the NSCDC have collaborated with other law enforcement agencies in the country to protect the pipelines in Nigeria. They have been able to catch and arrest and prosecute vandals on several occasions. On the Effects and implications of pipeline vandalism to the Nigeria society; pipeline vandalism has created the scarcity of oil production in the community (Asu 2016), Nigeria had witnessed environmental degradation and loss of economic activities of the communities due to pipeline vandalism (Alohan, 2013). Also, pipeline vandalism has created environmental pollution to the community (Ogbuefin, 2007).

The NSCDC is facing some problems hindering it from performing its work effectively. Some of the problems faces as gathered from respondents answer are; the problems of corruption (Asu 2016), lack of proper funding in its efforts to combat oil pipelines vandalism in Nigeria. Also, the agreement made by majority of the respondents led to the conclusion that areas of oil pipelines in the country lacks effective security arrangements. The members of the community also contribute into the increase rate of pipeline vandalism by not reporting cases of pipeline vandalism to the appropriate authority.

This research has also been able to identify internal security challenges in Nigeria. The present state of insecurity in Nigeria makes it crucial that the capacity of security agencies be built to prevent and respond to them. The NSCDC within its constitutional responsibilities has been responding to the issue of internal security threats. It is evident that the NSCDC has discharged its mandate to a satisfactory level of providing safety and security to Nigerians. The Corps has demonstrated civility in handling security and safety assignments. Through dialogue, negotiation, debate, public enlightenment and civic education, the agency has contributed positively to the management of internal security in Nigeria. In spite of some of its challenges, the Corps has demonstrated a high level of professionalism in security matters. In conclusion, there is a great need for the government to improve the recruitment and training process of NSCDC. This will enhance their skills in combating crimes and managing internal security threats.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The government should give NSCDC more political and constitutional power and make some funds available for combating boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and especially vandalisation in the country.
- ii. Stiffer punishment should be given to any security agents who conspires or aid and abet boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism in the country.
- iii. Employment should be created to fill in the gap of unemployment as a cause for people who engage in boko-haram, banditry, fulani-herdsmen, kidnapping and pipeline vandalism.
- iv. Officers and men of NSCDC should be motivated with well-paid salaries and other important facilities should be made available to them.
- v. The Corps and communities around the pipeline and where boko-haram, Fulani-herdsmen and banditry are operating in Nigeria should always organize effective neighborhood watch otherwise

known as vigilante group to protect the pipeline facilities and people living within the neighborhood.

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